

The Protective Effect of Inhaled Terbutaline, Sodium Cromoglycate and Budesonide on Exercise-induced Asthma in Children

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In asthmatic children vigorous exercise is often followed by clinical signs and symptoms of the acute, transitory increase in airway resistance (1-3). Strenuous exercise in the laboratory can elicit exercise-induced asthma (EIA) in 70-80 per cent of asthmatic patients⁽²⁾. EIA causes restriction to activities of asthmatic children. One of the goals of asthma management is to improve the patient's quality of life by allowing the patients to maintain normal activity level, including exercise. Drugs normally used for the treatment of asthma, i.e., β -agonist, sodium cromoglycate, corticosteroids have been used to reduce and block EIA; however, the protective effect of drugs has never been studied in Thai asthmatic children. Therefore, in the initial study, we studied the immediate protective effect of a single dose of inhaled terbutaline, sodium cromoglycate, budesonide on EIA in Thai asthmatic children.

METHOD

Fourteen patients with a history of asthma provoked by exertion entered an exercise challenge test. All patients had been treated in the Pediatric Allergy clinic at Maharat Nakhon Ratchasima Hospital for more than 1 year. Only 11 patients whose tests showed a fall of more than 20 per cent in forced expiratory volume in one second

(FEV₁) after exercise were recruited for the study⁽⁴⁾. There were 8 boys and 3 girls with an average age of 11 years (range 9-14). Medication that could influence the pulmonary response was withheld prior to exercise. Methylxanthine and β -agonist were not used for 8 hours, or 12 hours in case of extended-action formulations. Sodium cromoglycate and corticosteroids were not used for 24 hours. No patients had hypertension, heart disease, thyrotoxicosis, active bronchospasm, or upper respiratory tract infection on the day of exercise test. There were no patients receiving oral or inhaled corticosteroids, antihistamine, and anticholinergic drugs.

Exercises were performed on a constant-load exercise bicycle for 7-8 minutes. The speed was adjusted so that the patient's heart rates exceeded 170 bpm (85% of the predicted age-specific maximum heart rate) during the last 6 minutes of the test. The exercise test was stopped if there was one or more of the following: significant respiratory distress, a drop of 10 per cent in SaO₂ or below 85 per cent, chest pain, or at the patient request. The room temperature was between 23-25°C and the relative humidity ranged from 65 to 75 per cent. The same setting and duration were used for each test in any one patient. The effect of placebo, β -agonist, sodium cromoglycate, corti-

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costeroids were studied at the same time of day, with a 7 day interval between tests, within a period of 45 days. The exercise test would be postponed if on the day of the study the subject had a less than 80 per cent predicted normal FEV₁ level. Each subject inhaled placebo, or 200 µg of terbutaline, or 10 mg sodium cromoglycate, or 100 µg of budesonide 15 minutes before exercise tests. Forced vital capacity (FVC), forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁), maximum mid expiratory flow rate (MMEF), and peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) were measured with a dry spirometer (Microspiro Hi-501, Chest corporation, Japan). The pulmonary function was measured before exercise, immediately after and at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 minutes after exercise, the best of three attempts being used for analysis. The FEV₁ response to exercise was expressed as the maximum percentage fall in FEV₁ from the pre-exercise baseline. Responses to each drug were compared by Student's paired *t* test⁽⁵⁾.

RESULT

The mean (SEM) pre-exercise FEV₁ on each occasion did not differ significantly: placebo

1430 (133.80), terbutaline 1400 (137.89), sodium cromoglycate 1366 (156.97), budesonide 1336 (184.14). Mean FEV₁ before and for 25 minutes after exercise is shown in Fig. 1. After exercise the mean (SEM) maximum percentage fall in FEV₁ after placebo, 200 µg of terbutaline, 10 mg sodium cromoglycate, and 100 µg of budesonide were 22.81 (3.45), 4.05 (2.11), 11.29 (1.18), and 20.36 (2.33) respectively (Table 1). The mean percentage fall in FEV₁ after exercise for inhaled terbutaline and sodium cromoglycate was significantly less than the placebo ($p = 0.0004$ and $p = 0.006$). There was no significant difference between the values for placebo and budesonide ($p = 0.2737$).

DISCUSSION

The standard asthma management program is being accepted worldwide⁽¹⁾. Because exercise is the most frequent stimulation for provoking an asthmatic attack in children, the physical activity and quality of life of those children is disturbed by EIA. Physical training alone has controversial effects in the reduction of severity of EIA⁽⁶⁻⁷⁾. Although the exact pathogenesis of EIA remains unclear, pharmacological agents have

Fig. 1 FEV₁ before and after exercise in 11 asthmatic patients after drugs.

Table 1. Maximum percentage falls in FEV₁ after exercise in 11 asthmatic patients after placebo, terbutaline, sodium cromoglycate, budesonide

Patient	Placebo	Terbutaline	Na Cromoglycate	Budesonide
1	19.55	0.53	4.74	16.36
2	36.36	13.38	14.79	27.87
3	20.16	11.54	14.29	20.62
4	25.12	0.57	16.94	35.09
5	26.09	14.66	16.67	23.53
6	30.89	2.54	9.52	31.03
7	40.80	13.89	14.38	19.54
8	31.54	8.70	11.20	18.97
9	18.73	4.18	15.06	19.84
10	22.34	4.00	10.84	16.00
11	38.98	5.69	13.79	30.88

been shown to prevent EIA under the explanation of its having a direct effect on the bronchial smooth muscle, inhibiting the bronchoactive substances release, preventing mucosal edema, modulate vagal activity, or modifying changes in airway temperature and osmolarity. The inhalation of short acting β -agonist before exercise is recommended to prevent EIA^(1,2). However, sodium cromoglycate, nedocromil, corticosteroids, anticholinergic agents have been demonstrated to modulate EIA⁽⁸⁻¹¹⁾.

This study tried to demonstrate the immediate effect of a single dose of drugs which are normally used in treatment of the disease in Thai asthmatic children. The results showed that a short acting β -agonist, terbutaline, produced the smallest reductions in FEV₁ after exercise when compared with that of sodium cromoglycate, budesonide, and placebo. Sodium cromoglycate also prevented EIA whereas budesonide did not. This result is similar to the previous study of a single dose before exercise⁽¹²⁾. However, inhaled corticosteroids had shown to give a protective effect on EIA after prolonged treatment⁽¹¹⁾.

Using the unblind method in this study was a limitation. Further double blind crossover studies should be performed to better confirm the comparing effect of these drugs with that of placebo in Thai asthmatic children.

SUMMARY

The effect of single-dose inhaled terbutaline, sodium cromoglycate and budesonide were compared with control in 11 exercise-induced asthma (EIA) patients, aged 9-14 years. Patients exercise for 6 minutes, 15 minutes after inhaling drugs. The FVC, FEV₁, PEF and MMEF were recorded before exercise and after exercise at 5 minutes interval up to 25 minutes. After exercise, the mean (SEM) maximal percentage fall in FEV₁ after placebo, 200 μ g of terbutaline, 10 mg of sodium cromoglycate, and 100 μ g of budesonide were 22.81 (3.45), 4.05 (2.11), 11.29 (1.18), and 20.36 (2.33) respectively. It was concluded that single-dose inhaled terbutaline and sodium cromoglycate resulted in a significant protective effect on exercise-induced asthma whereas budesonide did not.

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การเปรียบเทียบผลของเทอบูทาลีน, โซเดียม โครโมกลัยเคท และบูติโซไนด์ ชนิดสูดดม ในการป้องกันอาการหอบจากการออกกำลังกายในเด็ก

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ได้ทำการศึกษาผลการป้องกันการเกิด exercise-induced asthma ในผู้ป่วยเด็ก 11 ราย อายุระหว่าง 9-14 ปี โดยใช้ single-dose inhaled terbutaline, sodium cromoglycate และ budesonide ก่อนเริ่ม exercise 15 นาที และใช้เวลา exercise 6 นาที จากนั้นวัดค่า FVC, FEV₁, PEFR & MMEF ทุก 5 นาที จนถึง 25 นาที พบว่า mean (SEM) maximal percentage fall ของค่า FEV₁ ภายหลังจากได้รับ placebo, terbutaline 200 mg, sodium cromoglycate 10 mg และ budesonide 100 mg เป็น 22.81 (3.45), 4.05 (2.11), 11.29 (1.18) และ 20.36 (2.33) ตามลำดับ

สรุปได้ว่า inhaled terbutaline และ sodium cromoglycate สามารถป้องกันการเกิด exercise-induced asthma ได้ ส่วน budesonide ป้องกันไม่ได้

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